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Historical Sciences

HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVES ON SPORTS IN RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article examines the development of physical culture and sports in historical retrospect in Russia. It is shown that the development of sports in Russia is conditioned by the need to form a harmoniously developed personality as the highest social value, which will contribute to strengthening people's health and increasing life expectancy. However, in recent years, there has been an alarming trend of deterioration in the health of the population. This is due not only to the problems of the economy, ecology, labor and everyday life, but also to the underestimation in society of socio-economic and health-improving processes of the formation of physical culture, which affected the residual principle of its financing, an acute shortage of material resources, qualified specialists. The current situation and, in particular, the sharp reduction in the number of people engaged in physical culture associated with it, led to a number of undesirable social phenomena. The importance of the role of physical culture and sports is currently supported by President Vladimir Putin.

Keywords: sports, Russia, state, society, patriotism.

I. INTRODUCTION

Regular physical culture and sports are a universal mechanism for maintaining and strengthening health, increasing the working capacity of the population. That is why the field of physical culture and sports contributes to the increase in the healthy life expectancy of the population. The Government of the Russian Federation was instructed to ensure the involvement of at least 55.0% of the country's population in systematic physical culture and sports by 2024 by creating appropriate conditions for all categories and groups of the population, increasing the level of provision with sports facilities and developing the sports reserve training system.

The solution of the task is carried out within the framework of the implementation of the national project "Demography" and the federal project included in it "Creation for all categories and groups of the population of conditions for physical culture and sports, mass sports, including increasing the level of provision of the population with sports facilities, as well as preparation of the sports reserve.

In all constituent entities of the Russian Federation, regional programs for the development of physical culture and sports and regional projects "Sport is the norm of life" have been approved.

II. METHODOLOGY

The theoretical prerequisites for the study are: the general theory of physical culture and its main provisions from the standpoint of a socio-pedagogical phenomenon (N.I. Ponomarev, 1996), physical culture and sports activities as a backbone factor of physical culture (V.M. Vydrin, 1997), the values of physical culture and the foundations of physical education (L.I. Lubysheva, 1992, 1996), the principles of individualization and differentiation in physical education (V.P. Ilyin, 1994), the relationship of physical culture and social activity (P.A. Vinogradov, 1990, 1992), socio-psychological determinants of a healthy lifestyle (M.Ya. Vilensky, 1999), the integration content of physical culture (Yu.M. Nikolaev, 1998), the correlation of basic concepts in the theory of physical culture (B.F. Evstafiev), systems of diagnostic methods in sports pedagogy (V.A. Bulkin, 1987), the theory of adaptive physical culture (SP. Evseev, 2002), the place of physical culture in the system of cultural phenomena (V.I. Stolyarov, 1997), principles of sociocultural analysis of human corporality.

III. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

On June 27, 1923, the decree of the Central Executive Committee of the RSFSR on the formation of Higher and local councils of physical culture, workers of the RSFSR, created a unified management structure for the physical culture and sports movement in the country, which was subsequently reformed many times.

For example, in the period from 1959 to 1968, physical culture and sports were recognized as constitutional values, the task was to promote the unification of citizens into sports organizations, in connection with which the committees on physical culture and sports were abolished and the leadership of physical culture in the country was transferred to a public organization - the Union of Sports Societies and Organizations, which significantly weakened the role of states in the development of physical culture and sports. Since 1968, the system of committees on physical culture and sports has been restored in the country again.

In the Russian Federation, the state policy in the field of physical culture and sports is considered as an element of the concept of a social state that ensures the involvement of more citizens in physical culture and sports; the development of sports infrastructure; the formation of values of a healthy lifestyle; regulatory legal regulation; the formation of a system of state guarantees.

The federal executive authority implementing the state policy in the field of physical culture and sports is currently the Ministry of Sports of the Russian Federation (Ministry of Sports of Russia).

In addition to state authorities, public and physical culture and sports organizations are involved in the management system of physical culture and sports, such as the Olympic, Paralympic, Deaflympic Committees of Russia, the Special Olympics of Russia, the Russian Student Sports Union, Physical Culture and Sports societies, sports federations by sports.

Currently in the Russian Federation there are sports societies "Dynamo", "Spartak", "DOSAAF", "Youth of Russia", "Atom-sport", "Harvest", "Locomotive". The development of physical culture and sports among military personnel is attributed to the powers of the Central Sports Club of the Army (CSKA). In 2018, the VFSSO "Labor Reserves" was created, whose activities are aimed at the development of physical culture and sports among workers in the industrial and energy sectors.

In order to attract the general physical culture and sports community to discuss problems and make decisions, including managerial ones, a Public Council, various commissions, scientific and methodological and expert councils have been established under the Ministry of Sports of Russia.

The subjects of the Russian Federation and municipalities have their own systems of physical culture and sports management, which differ in a wide variety of forms. At the same time, the analysis shows that the choice of management forms is not related to the population of the subjects of the Russian Federation and municipalities, their financial support and is purely subjective. The vertical of executive authorities in the field of physical culture and sports turned out to be heterogeneous both at the level of the subjects of the Russian Federation and at the municipal level. In accordance with the Law on the OGVSFR, the structure of the executive bodies of state power of the subject of the Russian Federation is determined by the highest official of the subject of the Russian Federation. Thus, according to the legislation of the Russian Federation, both the subjects of the Russian Federation and municipalities are completely independent in choosing the management structure, including in the field of physical culture and sports.

So, in 2019, in the subjects of the Russian Federation, the implementation of the state policy in the field of physical culture and sports is carried out:

49 ministries (13 of them combined with youth policy or tourism); 13 committees (1 combined); 1 agency; 13 departments (4 of them combined); 8 departments (1 of them combined); 1 sector (combined). Thus, in 20 subjects of the Russian Federation (23.5%), governing bodies in the field of physical culture and sports are combined with other areas of work.

The system of management of the sphere of physical culture and sports in the subjects of the Russian Federation, local self-government bodies of urban districts and municipal districts in the Russian Federation is not unified. At the same time, the practice of creating integrated (mixed) management bodies and structural units on issues of culture, physical culture and sports, tourism, education, youth policy, etc. is widespread.

The system of executive authorities of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation in the field of physical culture and sports (in %)

Without the right to participate in personnel policy and deep coordination of activities, it is impossible to create a strong vertical of management in any industry. Strengthening the centralization of management in the field of physical culture and sports will ensure more constructive interaction between the federal executive authorities and the executive authorities of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation and will contribute to the rational concentration of federal, regional and municipal personnel, material, technical and financial resources in priority areas.

Analyzing staffing, it should be noted that in 2018, more than 383.8 thousand full-time specialists in physical culture and sports worked in the field of physical culture and sports.

The provision of conditions for the development of physical culture and the organization of physical culture and sports work with various categories of the population in accordance with the Law on Local Self-Government and the Law on Sports are classified as issues of local importance.

At the end of 2018, the share of the population systematically engaged in physical culture and sports amounted to 39.8% (54.2 million people). Compared to 2017, the number of people involved increased by 4.1 million people.

The proportion of the rural population involved in physical culture and sports amounted to 34.9%, while the planned figure was 32.5%.

The share of children and youth involved in sports was 81.2%, the planned value for 2018 was 79.0%. Compared to 2017, more than 1.4 million people were involved in physical culture and sports in addition.

More than 17.0 million citizens of middle and older age are engaged in physical culture, which is 2.8 million more than in 2017. In percentage terms, the figures are 24.9% and 8.2%, respectively.

An important role in attracting young people to physical culture and sports is played by the created sports leagues in various sports. ANO "United Basketball League", in cooperation with the league's sponsors, has been the organizer of several regional projects for many years. For example, in cooperation with AK Alrosa, a project of the Sports and Music Festival "Mood" was developed, within the framework of which master classes are held for residents of the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia), open lessons in educational institutions (according to the methodology of teaching basketball in physical education classes), exhibition matches, documentaries about

basketball and a healthy lifestyle are shown. This project increased interest in basketball, a children's basketball club was created in Mirny, which this season became a participant in the final stage of the School Basketball League. The format of the festival "Mood" has been expanded, in addition to basketball, its program includes such sports as freestyle wrestling, hockey, acrobatic rock and roll, martial arts, cinema, ballet.

IV. CONCLUSION

An analysis of information materials received from all subjects of the Russian Federation, federal executive authorities, all-Russian physical culture and sports and other organizations showed that the problems in the development of physical culture and sports relate approximately equally to all levels of the power vertical: federal level - 32.0%, regional - 37.0%, municipal - 31.0%.

The main problems are identified - insufficient personnel and financial support for the industry, an insufficiently effective system for managing the sphere of physical culture and sports at the municipal level.

In order to implement the Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated May 7, 2018 №. 204 "On national goals and strategic objectives of the development of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2024", it is necessary to take additional measures to ensure intersectoral coordination and interaction of federal executive authorities, authorities of constituent entities of the Russian Federation, municipalities, as well as interested organizations.

Specific mechanisms for implementing the Decree of the President of the Russian Federation, as well as strategic goals and objectives for the development of physical culture and sports for the period after 2024 will be fixed in the Strategy for the Development of Physical Culture and Sports in the Russian Federation, currently being developed by the Ministry of Sports of Russia, designed for the period up to 2030.

To ensure the involvement of at least 55.0% of the country's population in systematic physical culture and sports by 2024, it is necessary to create appropriate conditions and opportunities for physical culture and sports of all categories and groups of the population, to increase the level of provision of the population with sports facilities and the development of the sports reserve training system.

Special attention should be paid to the issues of creating conditions for physical culture and sports, the search for new forms of physical culture and sports work with the population in the subjects of the Russian Federation that have low rates of population involvement in systematic physical culture and sports.

The priority tasks of the subjects of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2030 are:

- financial support and implementation of activities of regional and municipal programs for the development of physical culture and sports;
- implementation (currently being developed by the Ministry of Sports of Russia) strategies for the development of physical culture and sports in the Russian Federation for the period up to 2030;
- solving the issues of financing the construction, maintenance and overhaul of sports facilities, equipping them with the necessary high-quality and safe for use sports equipment, and equipment.

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ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ СПОРТА В РОССИИ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается развитие физической культуры и спорта в исторической ретроспективе в России. Показано, что развитие спорта в России обусловлено необходимостью формирования гармонично развитой личности как высшей социальной ценности, которая будет способствовать укреплению здоровья людей и увеличению продолжительности жизни. Однако в последние годы наблюдается тревожная тенденция ухудшения состояния здоровья населения. Это связано не только с проблемами экономики, экологии, труда и быта, но и с недооценкой в обществе социально-экономических и оздоровительных процессов формирования физической культуры, что сказалось на остаточном принципе ее финансирования, острой нехватке материальных ресурсов, квалифицированных специалистов. Сложившаяся ситуация и, в частности, связанное с ней резкое сокращение числа людей, занимающихся физической культурой, привели к ряду нежелательных социальных явлений. Важность роли физической культуры и спорта в настоящее время поддерживается Президентом Владимиром Путиным.

Ключевые слова: спорт, Россия, государство, общество, патриотизм.

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